

Shared and Unique Changes in Brain Connectivity Among Depressed Patients After Remission With Pharmacotherapy Versus Psychotherapy

- The study involved 131 patients who completed treatment and had usable MRI scans at baseline and week 12. Of these, 49.5% of patients treated with medication and 47.5% treated with cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) achieved remission. A significant common change in functional connectivity (rsFC) was observed in both treatment groups, specifically reduced connectivity between the subcallosal cingulate (SCC) and the left medial motor cortex (mM1). This change was exclusive to remitters and not seen in nonresponders or partial responders.
- Treatment-specific changes were also identified: CBT remitters showed increased rsFC between the posterior cingulate cortex (PCC) and superior frontal cortex, while medication remitters exhibited reduced connectivity between PCC and the middle frontal cortex. Additionally, CBT remitters demonstrated higher connectivity in the executive control network (ECN) and salience network (SN), particularly with regions involved in attention and cognitive control, compared to medication remitters and healthy controls. Medication remitters did not show significant differences from healthy controls at week 12.
- The results suggest that CBT and medication each lead to distinct patterns of rsFC changes, with CBT particularly enhancing attentional control and salience processing. Furthermore, changes in rsFC were more pronounced in remitters, supporting the idea that connectivity alterations are associated with remission rather than just symptom improvement.
- Figure 1: Illustrated in panel A, both CBT- and medication-treated remitters exhibited shared changes in rsFC from baseline to week 12. The inset provides a detailed view of the overlapping region in the mM1, highlighting the specific voxels where significant changes occurred in medication-treated (red) and CBT-treated (green) remitters, with their overlapping area shown in yellow. The violin plot indicates that both treatment groups experienced similar reductions in the overlap cluster, and at week 12, the SCC-mM1 connectivity in remitters was significantly lower than in healthy control subjects. Panel B shows changes in SCC rsFC from baseline to week 12 for both CBT and

medication completers, accounting for response status. Both treatments were linked to reductions in SCC-mM1 rsFC, but no overlapping voxels were found. The violin plots demonstrate no significant change in medication-treated patients when analyzing the center of mass in the significant CBT mM1 cluster, and no significant change in CBT-treated patients when analyzing the center of mass in the significant medication mM1 cluster. Panel C displays the unique rsFC changes from baseline to week 12 that significantly differed between CBT and medication remitters.

- Figure 2: Panel A illustrates changes in functional connectivity in patients who remitted with CBT, while panel B shows these changes in patients who remitted with antidepressant medication. The schematic diagrams, based on the results from Figure 1 and Table S2 in the online supplement, highlight the regions where functional connectivity changes occurred, marked in green. The dark blue arc in both diagrams represents reduced connectivity between the subcallosal cingulate (SCC) and somatomotor cortex in both CBT and medication remitters. The red arcs in the CBT schematic show increased connectivity from baseline to week 12 among CBT remitters, while the light blue arcs in the antidepressant medication schematic depict decreased connectivity in medication remitters. Key regions labeled include the anterior insula (ANT INS), dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC), posterior cingulate cortex (PCC), and subcallosal cingulate cortex (SCC).
- Table 1: Baseline characteristics of participants in a study of brain connectivity after remission from major depressive disorder with antidepressant medication treatment or CBTa
- Tables S1–S4 in the online supplement present the permuted within-treatment changes in resting-state functional connectivity (rsFC) among patients who achieved remission with CBT or medication for the four seeds. No statistically significant differences (all p values > 0.2) were found between medication- and CBT-treated patients on any demographic or clinical variables. Additionally, there were no significant differences in age or sex between the major depression and healthy control groups. CBT = cognitive-behavioral therapy; HAMD = Hamilton Depression Rating Scale; HAM-A = Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale.
- Table 2: Table illustrated changes in resting-state functional connectivity between the subcallosal cingulate cortex and the medial motor cortex based on outcome group.
- Table 3: The centers of mass and cluster sizes for each region are listed in Table 3. Green represents CBT-treated patients, red represents medication-treated patients, and blue represents healthy controls. Solid green or red lines indicate statistically

significant changes ($p < 0.005$) within each treatment group, while dashed lines represent changes with p-values between 0.005 and 0.05. Statistically significant differences between patients and healthy controls are marked by dotted ($p < 0.05$) or solid ($p < 0.01$) blue lines at the top of the plots. Statistically significant differences between treatment groups at baseline or week 12 are shown by dotted ($p < 0.05$) or solid ($p < 0.01$) black lines at the bottom of the plots.

Authors

- **Boadie Dunlop**- Department of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences Professor
 - Co-Director, Emory Center for Psychedelics and Spirituality, Emory University
 - Director, Adult Outpatient Programs, Department of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences, Emory University School of Medicine
 - Professor, Department of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences, Emory University School of Medicine
 - Medical Director, Emory Healthcare Veterans Program, Emory University
 - Medical Director, Emory Veterans Program, Department of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences, Emory University School of Medicine
 - Director, Mood and Anxiety Disorders Program, Emory University

Degrees

- MS in Clinical Research from Emory University
- MD from Mayo Medical School
- BA from Washington University

Publications

- Rapid Effects of MDMA Administration on Self-Reported Personality Traits and Affect State: A Randomized, Placebo-Controlled Trial in Healthy Adults.
- Acylcarnitines metabolism in depression: association with diagnostic status, depression severity and symptom profile in the NESDA cohort.

- A framework for assessment of adverse events occurring in psychedelic-assisted therapies.
- The capacity of brain circuits to enhance psychiatry.
- The metabolome-wide signature of major depressive disorder.
- Metabolomics Signatures of serotonin reuptake inhibitor (Escitalopram), serotonin norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor (Duloxetine) and Cognitive Behavior Therapy on Key Neurotransmitter Pathways in Major Depressive Disorder.

- **Jungho Cha**

- Nash Family Center for Advanced Circuit Therapeutics · Radiology PhD
- Indeks Hirsha- 20

Publications

- Choroid Plexus Volume, Amyloid Burden, and Cognition in the Alzheimer's Disease Continuum
- Different effect of hypo- and hypermetabolism on cognition in dementia with Lewy bodies: are they coupled or independent?
- Whole brain network effects of subcallosal cingulate deep brain stimulation for treatment-resistant depression
- Cingulate dynamics track depression recovery with deep brain stimulation
- Distinct amyloid-dependent patterns of nigra dopamine depletion in Lewy body diseases

- **Ki Sueng Choi**

- Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai
- Index Hirsha – 32

Publications :

- Defining critical white matter pathways mediating successful subcallosal cingulate deep brain stimulation for treatment-resistant depression
- A connectomic approach for subcallosal cingulate deep brain stimulation surgery: prospective targeting in treatment-resistant depression
- Functional connectivity of the subcallosal cingulate cortex and differential outcomes to treatment with cognitive-behavioral therapy or antidepressant medication for major
- Brain stimulation and brain lesions converge on common causal circuits in neuropsychiatric disease

- **Justin K. Rajendra**

- Staff - National Institute of Mental Health
- Index Hirsha - 15

Publications :

- Defining critical white matter pathways mediating successful subcallosal cingulate deep brain stimulation for treatment-resistant depression
- A connectomic approach for subcallosal cingulate deep brain stimulation surgery: prospective targeting in treatment-resistant depression
- White matter integrity is a stronger predictor of motor function than BOLD response in patients with stroke
- Handling multiplicity in neuroimaging through Bayesian lenses with multilevel modeling
- Brain activation in primary motor and somatosensory cortices during motor imagery correlates with motor imagery ability in stroke patients

- **Charles B. Nemeroff**

- Professor of Psychiatry, University of Texas at Austin Dell Medical School
- Index Hirsha – 188

Publications :

- The role of childhood trauma in the neurobiology of mood and anxiety disorders: preclinical and clinical studies
- Pituitary-adrenal and autonomic responses to stress in women after sexual and physical abuse in childhood
- The relationship of depression to cardiovascular disease: epidemiology, biology, and treatment
- Depression, desperation, and suicidal ideation in college students: results from the American Foundation for Suicide Prevention College Screening Project at Emory University
- Childhood trauma associated with smaller hippocampal volume in women with major depression

- **W. Edward Craighead**

- Department of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences and Department of Psychology, Emory University

Publications :

- Effects of exercise training on older patients with major depression
- Exercise treatment for major depression: maintenance of therapeutic benefit at 10 months
- Normative and reliability data for the Children's Depression Inventory
- Neurobiological and psychiatric consequences of child abuse and neglect
- The role of nonspecific factors in cognitive-behavior therapy for depression.

- **Helen Mayberg MD**

- Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai
- Index Hirsha - 114

Publications :

- Deep brain stimulation for treatment-resistant depression
- Toward discovery science of human brain function

- Reciprocal limbic-cortical function and negative mood: converging PET findings in depression and normal sadness
- Resting-state connectivity biomarkers define neurophysiological subtypes of depression
- Limbic-cortical dysregulation: a proposed model of depression.
- Attending to the present: mindfulness meditation reveals distinct neural modes of self-reference.

About The American Journal of Psychiatry

- The American Journal of Psychiatry is the most widely read psychiatric publication globally. Issued monthly, it is a crucial resource for psychiatrists and mental health professionals who need to stay informed on the latest developments across all areas of psychiatry. No other journal in the field reaches as many psychiatrists with such significant impact and immediacy. It is regarded as an essential journal by the vast majority of psychiatrists. The first volume was issued in 1844, at which time it was known as the *American Journal of Insanity*. The title changed to the current form with the July issue of 1921.
2023 Impact Factor: 15.1
- According to the *Journal Citation Reports*, the journal has a 2020 impact factor of 18.112.